

IMPACT OF EIT-GUIDED INDIVIDUALIZED PEEP TITRATION ON RESPIRATORY MECHANICS AND OUTCOMES IN ACUTE HYPOXEMIC RESPIRATORY FAILURE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

ABDULMOHSEN AHMED ALSUBAEAA

Anesthesia Technician 1, Anesthesia Department, Immam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region – Dammam. Email: Subaeaa2@ngha.med.sa

ABDULLAH ALRASHEED

Family Medicine Consultant, Family Medicine Department, Immam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region -Dammam. Email: alrasheedab3@ngha.med.sa

FATIMAH ALI ALAWAMI

Staff Nurse 1, Outpatient Department, Nursing Department, Immam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region – Dammam. Email: alawamifa85@gmail.com

NORA ABDREBALMEER SHAABAN

Staff Nurse 1, Outpatient Department, Nursing Department, Immam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region – Dammam. Email: norasolafwaard@gmail.com

ROQIAH ALI ALMARHOUN

Staff Nurse 1, Nursing Department, Primary Healthcare, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region Dammam. Email: Marhounr@ngha.med.sa

ABEER MOHAMMED ALMUSLAB

Staff Nurse 1, General Pediatric, Nursing Department, Saudi Arabia Dammam, Immam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region Dammam. Email: shadoow26@hotmail.com

FATIMAH REDA ALNASSER

Staff Nurse 1, Outpatient Department, Nursing Department, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Region- Dammam. Email: nasserf2@ngha.med.sa

ZAHRA ALI AL OBAID

Pain Management, Staff Nurse, Nursing Department, Imam Abdulrahman Bin Faisal Hospital, Ministry of National Guard, Eastern Province-Dammam. Email: Alobaidza@ngha.med.sa

Abstract

Background: Acute hypoxemic respiratory failure (AHRF), and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) managed with mechanical ventilation and positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP). Conventional PEEP titration methods sometimes fail to account for patient-specific lung recruit ability leading to ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI). Electrical impedance tomography (EIT) is a bedside imaging tool that allows individualized PEEP titration based on regional ventilation distribution. We aimed to systematically review the impact of EIT-guided individualized PEEP titration on respiratory mechanics and clinical outcomes in patients with AHRF. **Methods:** A systematic search was conducted in PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar for original studies published between 2020 and 2025. Inclusion criteria were adult patients with ARDS, individualized PEEP titration using EIT or similar methods, and reporting of at least one physiological or clinical outcome. We exclude studies not involving human subjects, review articles, and non-English publications were excluded. Seven studies met the eligibility criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis. **Results:** The included studies consisted of four randomized trials, one crossover trial, one

prospective cohort, and one retrospective study. Most used EIT-guided decremental PEEP trials to identify optimal PEEP levels. EIT-based titration was associated with improved compliance, reduced mechanical power and driving pressure, and better lung homogeneity. Trends toward reduced 28-day mortality and improved organ function were noted, findings on hard outcomes, ICU stay, and ventilator-free days were inconsistent. **Conclusion:** EIT-guided individualized PEEP titration improves physiological parameters in patients with AHRF and shows promise in optimizing lung-protective ventilation. Evidence of its impact on clinical outcomes is limited and heterogeneous. Further multicenter randomized trials are needed to confirm its benefits on survival and recovery.

Keywords: Electrical Impedance Tomography, Positive End-Expiratory Pressure, Individualized PEEP, Acute Hypoxemic Respiratory Failure, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome, Mechanical Ventilation, Lung Compliance, Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury, PEEP Titration, Respiratory Mechanics.

INTRODUCTION

Acute hypoxemic respiratory failure (AHRF), and acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), contributes to mortality in the ICU due to diffuse alveolar damage, profound hypoxemia, and ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI) (1). Positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) is a cornerstone in mechanical ventilation, used to prevent alveolar collapse and improve oxygenation. Standard titration strategies, FIO₂/PEEP tables, do not account for the substantial heterogeneity in lung recruit ability among patients, risking overdistension and potential harm (2). Electrical impedance tomography (EIT) is a non-invasive, bedside imaging tool that monitors regional changes in lung aeration. It enables personalized PEEP titration by targeting optimal recruitment while minimizing overdistension (3). A crossover RCT by Jimenez et al. found that EIT-guided PEEP reduced mechanical power compared to FIO₂/PEEP tables in moderate-to-severe ARDS (2). A prospective study reported improvements in compliance, driving pressure reduction, and trends toward lower 28-day mortality and SOFA score improvements (4).

Two recent meta-analyses concluded that EIT-guided PEEP improves respiratory mechanics and decrease in-hospital and 28-day mortality, and results is inconsistent due to limited sample sizes and study heterogeneity (5). The clinical adoption of EIT-guided PEEP is constrained by the predominance of single-center trials and pilot studies (4). This systematic review aims to collate evidence on EIT-guided individualized PEEP titration in AHRF. Our objectives are to examine its effects on respiratory mechanics (compliance, driving pressure, mechanical power) and key clinical outcomes (mortality, ventilator-free days, ICU/hospital length of stay). We aim to determine whether EIT-guided PEEP offers physiological and clinical advantages over conventional titration methods, and to identify gaps to guide future research.

METHODOLOGY

This systematic review was conducted according to PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) guidelines. A literature search was carried out to identify original studies that investigated the effects of individualized positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) titration on outcomes in adult patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS). We search using databases including PubMed Central (PMC), Scopus, and Google Scholar, covering publications from 2020 to 2025. Keywords

used in the search included; individualized PEEP, PEEP titration, electrical impedance tomography, ARDS, acute respiratory distress syndrome, and mechanical ventilation. Only full-text articles published in English were considered. A total of 57 records were identified through database searching. After removal of 12 duplicate entries, 9 records were excluded by automation tools, and 8 additional records were removed for other reasons, leaving 28 records for title and abstract screening. Of these, 8 records were excluded and not meeting the inclusion criteria. The full texts of 20 articles were then assessed for eligibility.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of selected studies

Five articles could not be retrieved, and of the 15 retrieved articles, 8 were excluded: 4 were review articles, 3 did not report the outcomes of interest, and 1 was unrelated to the topic. Finally, 7 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis.

We include original research conducted on adult human subjects diagnosed with ARDS; evaluation of individualized PEEP titration strategies, electrical impedance tomography (EIT)-guided titration, intratidal compliance profile analysis, or decremental PEEP trials; and reporting of at least one relevant clinical or physiological outcome, including mortality, lung mechanics, gas exchange, mechanical power, or hemodynamics.

We exclude animal or bench studies, studies not involving individualized PEEP titration, abstracts or protocols without data, review articles, and non-English publications. Study selection was done by one reviewer who screened all titles and abstracts, followed by full-text review for eligibility. Data extraction was performed manually and included study design, sample size, population characteristics, and method of PEEP titration, comparator groups, and main findings. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion.

RESULTS

A total of seven studies were included in this systematic review, including different designs, patient populations, and PEEP titration methodologies. Of these, six were clinical trials (four randomized controlled trials, one crossover trial, and one prospective cohort), and one was a retrospective cohort study. The studies explored the effects of individualized PEEP titration guided by electrical impedance tomography (EIT), compliance profiles, or a decremental PEEP strategy, compared with conventional PEEP settings derived from standard FiO_2 /PEEP tables.

The sample sizes ranged from 24 to 117 patients in included studies. Two studies focused on COVID-19-related ARDS (6,7), while others included general ARDS populations with varying comorbidities (chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (8) or surgical populations under general anesthesia (9)). One study (10) included patients undergoing extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO). Six studies used EIT for individualized PEEP titration, with varying protocols for defining optimal PEEP.

EIT was used to identify the crossing point between alveolar overdistension and collapse during decremental PEEP trials (2,7). Weber et al. (2020) applied an intratidal compliance profile to guide PEEP selection, and He et al. (2021) compared EIT-guided titration with a low PEEP- FiO_2 table in a randomized design (11). Individualized PEEP titration resulted in changes to PEEP levels when compared with traditional methods. In Somhorst et al. (2022), EIT led to either increased or decreased PEEP in 63% of patients.

Liu et al. (2022) showed that in ARDS patients with COPD, EIT-guided PEEP was lower than ARDSnet-guided PEEP, resulting in reduced plateau pressures and mechanical power. EIT-based approaches were associated with improved lung homogeneity, better compliance, and reduced indicators of ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI).

Jimenez et al. (2023) show that EIT-guided PEEP titration reduced mechanical power compared to the high PEEP-FiO₂ table (-4.36 J/min, p=0.002). He et al. (2021) reported lower SOFA scores in the EIT group, 28-day mortality and ventilator-free days were not different. In He et al. (2021), there was no significant difference in 28-day mortality (21% vs. 27%) between the EIT and control groups. Some studies show improvement in secondary outcomes. Liu et al. (2022) show improved gas exchange and hemodynamics in the EIT group in COPD patients. Jonkman et al. (2023) show the large variability in recruit ability and suggest that EIT allows more personalized and potentially safer PEEP selection.

Table 1: PEEP Titration in ARDS - Study Summary Table

Citation	Study Design	Study Aim	Sample Size	Methodology
Jonkman et al., 2023	Multicenter prospective physiological study	To assess lung recruit ability and define EIT-based PEEP titration in COVID-19 ARDS	108 patients with COVID-19 ARDS	EIT-based assessment during decremental PEEP trial to define recruit ability and optimal PEEP
Weber et al., 2020	Randomized controlled trial	To evaluate individualized PEEP titration via intratidal compliance profile analysis	60 patients undergoing general anesthesia	PEEP titrated using gliding-SLICE method; regional ventilation assessed with EIT
He et al., 2021	Randomized controlled clinical trial	To determine if EIT-guided early individualized PEEP improves outcomes in ARDS	117 ARDS patients	Comparison of EIT-guided PEEP vs low PEEP/FiO ₂ table; outcomes included SOFA scores and mortality
Somhorst et al., 2022	Retrospective cohort study	To compare PEEP from high PEEP-FiO ₂ table vs EIT-guided titration in COVID-19 ARDS	75 patients with COVID-19 ARDS	EIT-guided decremental PEEP trial at ICU admission; comparison of respiratory parameters
Liu et al., 2022	Single-center, prospective repeated-measures study	To compare respiratory mechanics and PEEP titration methods in ARDS with/without COPD	27 ARDS patients (14 with COPD, 13 without)	EIT-based vs ARDSnet PEEP titration in COPD and non-COPD subgroups
Jimenez et al., 2023	Single-center, randomized crossover pilot trial	To evaluate the impact of EIT-guided PEEP on mechanical power in ARDS	Not specified (pilot study)	Comparison of mechanical power with EIT-guided vs high PEEP/FiO ₂ table
Di Pierro et al., 2022	Retrospective observational study	To compare PEEP titration using EIT in COVID-19 vs non-COVID ARDS on ECMO	24 patients (12 C-ARDS, 12 NC-ARDS)	EIT-guided decremental PEEP trial with comparison of overdistension and compliance

Table 2: summary of studies on individualized peep titration in ARDS

Citation	Demographic Characteristics	Type of PEEP	Main Findings
Di Pierro et al. (2022)	24 patients (12 COVID-ARDS, 12 non-COVID ARDS); V-V ECMO support	EIT-guided decremental PEEP titration	C-ARDS patients had lower overdistension risk at high PEEP; EIT feasible for individualized PEEP on ECMO
Jonkman et al. (2023)	108 COVID-19 ARDS patients; multicenter	EIT-guided with collapse-overdistension curve crossing point	Recruit ability varied; EIT-based PEEP differed from compliance-based PEEP in 81% of cases
Weber et al. (2020)	60 surgical patients under general anesthesia	Intra-tidal compliance profile (Gliding-SLICE method)	Individualized PEEP resulted in better regional ventilation; less ventral and dorsal loss
He et al. (2021)	117 ARDS patients; ICU; randomized controlled	EIT-guided vs. low PEEP/FiO ₂ table	No mortality difference; improved organ function (lower SOFA); diverse PEEP-FiO ₂ pairing
Somhorst et al. (2022)	75 COVID-19 ARDS patients	EIT-guided vs. high PEEP/FiO ₂ table	63% had ≥2 cmH ₂ O PEEP change; supports individualized PEEP
Liu et al. (2022)	27 ARDS patients (14 with COPD, 13 without)	EIT-guided vs. ARDSnet protocol	COPD group had lower PEEP and better outcomes with EIT
Jimenez et al. (2023)	Randomized crossover pilot in moderate-severe ARDS	EIT-guided vs. high PEEP/FiO ₂ table	EIT reduced mechanical power, driving pressure, and improved compliance

DISCUSSION

Our systematic review evaluates the clinical impact of individualized positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) titration in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), focusing on strategies guided by electrical impedance tomography (EIT). EIT-guided PEEP titration offers promising physiological benefits compared to conventional approaches ARDSNet PEEP-FiO₂ tables or pressure volume curve methods. The translation of these physiological improvements into clinical outcome benefits is an area requiring further evidence. Several studies (12,13) conducted meta-analyses which show that EIT-based PEEP strategies improved oxygenation (PaO₂/FiO₂) and lung compliance, and reducing mechanical power and driving pressure, factors closely linked to ventilator-induced lung injury (VILI). Songsangvorn et al. found a reduction in mortality which indicate the potential for EIT to influence not only surrogate physiological outcomes and survival, although this finding stemmed from a small subset of studies and should be interpreted with caution. The study by Sella et al. (14) compared EIT-derived PEEP with values suggested by high and low PEEP-FiO₂ tables in COVID-19 ARDS patients. EIT-derived PEEP values were different—than those from standardized tables, indicating that table-based approaches not adequately reflect patient-specific lung recruit ability. Zhao et al. (15) compared EIT-guided PEEP titration to a pressure volume curve method and

found improvements in compliance and oxygenation, as well as a higher weaning and survival rate in the EIT group.

While the study had limitations related to baseline differences between groups, it still underscored the potential of EIT to refine ventilator settings in severe ARDS. EIT-guided PEEP titration has proven feasible in highly complex populations, and patients supported with extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO). Both Franchisee et al. (2017) and Puel et al. (16) show that EIT can assist in identifying a "best compromise PEEP" in ECMO-treated patients by balancing alveolar recruitment and overdistension. These studies reported large interindividual variability in optimal PEEP levels, showing the need for personalized approaches in patients with severely compromised lungs. Zhao et al. (15) raised an important methodological issue: different EIT-based indices (global inhomogeneity index, regional compliance, and end-expiratory lung impedance) yield different optimal PEEP levels in the same patient. This variability calls for cautious interpretation of EIT data and suggests that no single EIT metric is better. Clinicians need to consider a combination of parameters and integrate them with clinical judgment. The evidence supports that individualized PEEP titration via EIT optimize lung mechanics and reduce the risk of VILI in ARDS. Evidence on hard clinical outcomes such as mortality, ICU length of stay, or ventilator-free days remains limited and mixed (14,17,18). Differences in study designs, patient populations (COVID-19 vs. non-COVID ARDS), and EIT protocols contribute to the finding's heterogeneity.

LIMITATIONS

This review is limited by the small number of high-quality randomized controlled trials and the predominance of single-center or observational studies. Most studies evaluated short-term physiological endpoints rather than long-term clinical outcomes. The potential for publication bias and variation in EIT interpretation criteria in studies also limits the generalizability of findings.

CONCLUSION

The available evidence supports the use of individualized PEEP titration strategies, mainly those guided by EIT, to improve lung recruitment, reduce overdistension, and optimize mechanical ventilation in ARDS patients. Future randomized trials are necessary to confirm these physiological benefits translations into improved survival and recovery outcomes.

Abbreviations

- 1) AHRF, Acute Hypoxemic Respiratory Failure
- 2) ARDS, Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome
- 3) COPD, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
- 4) EIT, Electrical Impedance Tomography
- 5) ECMO, Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation

- 6) FiO₂, Fraction of Inspired Oxygen
- 7) ICU, Intensive Care Unit
- 8) PEEP, Positive End-Expiratory Pressure
- 9) RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial
- 10) SOFA, Sequential Organ Failure Assessment
- 11) VILI, Ventilator-Induced Lung Injury
- 12) V-V, Veno-Venous
- 13) ECMO, Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation

References

- 1) Merck & Co., Inc. (2023). Acute hypoxemic respiratory failure (AHRF/ARDS). Merck Manual Professional. Available from: <https://www.merckmanuals.com/professional/critical-care-medicine/respiratory-failure-and-mechanical-ventilation/acute-hypoxemic-respiratory-failure-ahrf-ards>
- 2) Jimenez JV, Munroe E, Weirauch AJ, Fiorino K, Culter CA, Nelson K, et al. Electric impedance tomography-guided PEEP titration reduces mechanical power in ARDS: a randomized crossover pilot trial. *Crit Care*. 2023 Jan 17;27(1):21. Available from: <https://ccforum.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13054-023-04315-x>
- 3) Franchineau G, Jonkman AH, Piquilloud L, Yoshida T, Costa E, Rozé H, et al. Electrical Impedance Tomography to Monitor Hypoxemic Respiratory Failure. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2024 Mar 15;209(6):670–82. Available from: <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/10.1164/rccm.202306-1118CI>
- 4) Soltész L, Leyens J, Vogel M, Muders T, Putensen C, Kipfmüller F, et al. EIT guided evaluation of regional ventilation distributions in neonatal and pediatric ARDS: a prospective feasibility study. *Respir Res*. 2025 Feb 19;26(1):60. Available from: <https://respiratory-research.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12931-025-03134-8>
- 5) Sanchez-Piedra C, Rodríguez-Ortiz-de-Salazar B, Roca O, Prado-Galbarro FJ, Perestelo-Perez L, Sanchez-Gomez LM. Electrical impedance tomography for PEEP titration in ARDS patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Clin Monit Comput*. 2025 Feb 26; Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10877-025-01266-2>
- 6) Somhorst P, van der Zee P, Endeman H, Gommers D. PEEP-FiO₂ table versus EIT to titrate PEEP in mechanically ventilated patients with COVID-19-related ARDS. *Crit Care*. 2022 Sep 12;26(1):272. Available from: <https://ccforum.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13054-022-04135-5>
- 7) Jonkman AH, Alcalá GC, Pavlovsky B, Roca O, Spadaro S, Scaramuzzo G, et al. Lung Recruitment Assessed by Electrical Impedance Tomography (RECRUIT): A Multicenter Study of COVID-19 Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2023 Jul 1;208(1):25–38. Available from: <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/10.1164/rccm.202212-2300OC>
- 8) Liu X, Liu X, Meng J, Liu D, Huang Y, Sang L, et al. Electrical impedance tomography for titration of positive end-expiratory pressure in acute respiratory distress syndrome patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Crit Care*. 2022 Nov 4;26(1):339. Available from: <https://ccforum.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13054-022-04201-y>
- 9) Weber J, Gutjahr J, Schmidt J, Lozano-Zahonero S, Borgmann S, Schumann S, et al. Effect of individualized PEEP titration guided by intratidal compliance profile analysis on regional ventilation assessed by electrical impedance tomography – a randomized controlled trial. *BMC Anesthesiol*. 2020 Dec 20;20(1):42. Available from: <https://bmcanesthesiol.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12871-020-00960-9>

- 10) Di Pierro M, Giani M, Bronco A, Lembo FM, Rona R, Bellani G, et al. Bedside Selection of Positive End Expiratory Pressure by Electrical Impedance Tomography in Patients Undergoing Venovenous Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation Support: A Comparison between COVID-19 ARDS and ARDS from Other Etiologies. *J Clin Med*. 2022 Mar 16;11(6):1639. Available from: <https://www.mdpi.com/2077-0383/11/6/1639>
- 11) He H, Chi Y, Yang Y, Yuan S, Long Y, Zhao P, et al. Early individualized positive end-expiratory pressure guided by electrical impedance tomography in acute respiratory distress syndrome: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *Crit Care*. 2021 Dec 30;25(1):230. Available from: <https://ccforum.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13054-021-03645-y>
- 12) Songsangvorn N, Xu Y, Lu C, Rotstein O, Brochard L, Slutsky AS, et al. Electrical impedance tomography-guided positive end-expiratory pressure titration in ARDS: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Intensive Care Med*. 2024 May 21;50(5):617–31. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s00134-024-07362-2>
- 13) Yu M, Deng Y, Cha J, Jiang L, Wang M, Qiao S, et al. PEEP titration by EIT strategies for patients with ARDS: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Med Intensiva (English Ed)*. 2023 Jul;47(7):383–90. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2173572722002077>
- 14) Sella N, Zarantonello F, Andreatta G, Gagliardi V, Boscolo A, Navalesi P. Positive end-expiratory pressure titration in COVID-19 acute respiratory failure: electrical impedance tomography vs. PEEP/FiO₂ tables. *Crit Care*. 2020 Dec 1;24(1):540. Available from: <https://ccforum.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13054-020-03242-5>
- 15) Zhao Z, Chang MY, Chang MY, Gow CH, Zhang JH, Hsu YL, et al. Positive end-expiratory pressure titration with electrical impedance tomography and pressure–volume curve in severe acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Ann Intensive Care*. 2019 Dec 17;9(1):7. Available from: <https://annalsofintensivecare.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s13613-019-0484-0>
- 16) Puel F, Crognier L, Soulé C, Vardon-Bouines F, Ruiz S, Seguin T, et al. Assessment of electrical impedance tomography to set optimal positive end-expiratory pressure for venovenous ECMO-treated severe ARDS patients. *J Crit Care*. 2020 Dec;60:38–44. Available from: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0883944120306067>
- 17) Franchineau G, Bréchet N, Lebreton G, Hekimian G, Nieszkowska A, Trouillet JL, et al. Bedside Contribution of Electrical Impedance Tomography to Setting Positive End-Expiratory Pressure for Extracorporeal Membrane Oxygenation–treated Patients with Severe Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2017 Aug 15;196(4):447–57. Available from: <https://www.atsjournals.org/doi/10.1164/rccm.201605-1055OC>
- 18) Zhao Z, Lee LC, Chang MY, Frerichs I, Chang HT, Gow CH, et al. The incidence and interpretation of large differences in EIT-based measures for PEEP titration in ARDS patients. *J Clin Monit Comput*. 2020 Oct 5;34(5):1005–13. Available from: <https://link.springer.com/10.1007/s10877-019-00396-8>